

Homeasy: A Home Service App

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Abstract:- People today are overwhelmed with work since they all have hectic schedules and activities that keep them from spending time with their families. If they run into any unanticipated issues, they will have to pick between dealing with them and the task at hand. In such circumstances, everyone of us would have daydreamed about a particular kind of house without any leaky pipes or a house that has never needed maintenance. Since this is the ideal situation, we have undoubtedly imagined that life would be better if there were no obstacle standing in the way of receiving services at our doorstep. To build and develop a system that delivers several services to your door with only one tap, consider this idea. a service that offers a wide range of service providers, including painters, plumbers, carpenters, repairers, gardeners, and electricians. The system is flexible and allows you to arrange services from anywhere to wherever you choose.

Keywords:- maintenance, system, activities, services.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Cities and rural areas, we have seen many service providers looking for work at the junction of two roads or roadside. Sometimes they might get the work or sometimes they might not. There are many skilled service providers who do not get enough recognition and are in a need of platform to display their work and get employed. Many of the times they won't get works matching their skill level and expected wages. This leads to their unemployment and waste of human resource in their locality. During pandemic situation, local service providers are the ones who have suffered most to earn a living. This project is used to facilitate a system which directly connects users with service providers. The basic idea of our project is that someone sitting at home can hire service provider. There should be a proper platform in which service providers can show and utilize their skills. We are going to develop an app named "**Homeasy**" which connects service providers directly to their customers. Homeasy is an app for local service providers like Carpenter, cook, painter, plumber, electrician, landscapers, appliances repairer, construction workers, loggers and grass cutters. End users of this app are service providers and customers. It is embedded with many features that the service providers can utilize to their best. Along with the Service providers, customers will be benefited and will get to know about various skilled people around them. Service providers can use this app to find job and customers can use this app to find service as per their requirements. This app will be very useful during pandemic situation because service providers need not go out of the house in the search of job and customers can book workers by staying at home.

II. OBJECTIVE

The main purpose of Homeasy is about bringing home services to the doorstep with just one click. This paper is primarily about online home service theme, with many resources provided as well as how to order and deliver services at the doorstep. The online application for home service can be used by any authorized user who intends to claim it with a mobile application. To provide secured login module for customers and service providers and the admin by providing relevant details during registration. Designing a user-friendly interface for searching services. Providing a secure online payment gateway for service seekers. Acknowledging confirmation of user-selected services.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Many times, skilled or reliable providers are not readily available when someone needs assistance with tiny but significant household tasks, which always results in flawless service. When people relocate to a new city, they are not familiar with any local providers of domestic services. On the other hand, a large number of the town's competent service providers are unemployed and at home. The greatest way to link service providers and customers is through this. Our online service application is a very practical and effective way to arrange for home services.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dr. Shamshed, Nazim Ali, "**Daily wage labour marketworkers: Causes and consequences**", 2017[1] The current study aims to investigate the factors that influence labour market workers on a daily basis in Aligarh. The primary source of data used in the research was a city-specific questionnaire that was administered in 2015. When 193 daily labour market workers were randomly chosen and interviewed in the city of Aligarh, 10 locations where workers frequently waited for jobs were found, and a total of 3860 daily workers' families were documented. According to a survey analysis, almost 94% of workers on the daily labour market were under the age bracket (aged 15-59).

M.A.F.Ashfa, M.A.F. Sana Anjum, A.Ijas Mohamed, M.M.F. Aqeela, M.S. Zunoomy "**Daily wage workers in COVID-19 pandemic period**", 2021[2] The findings of this study demonstrate that, as a result of the high cost of living and the high cost of basic requirements, urban dwellers suffer more than those who make a living on a daily basis. The COVID-19 epidemic has had catastrophic impacts on every community and person, greatly harming the world economy. The wealthy and middle class, however, have enough money to cover their daily expenses. At the same time, employees who are paid on a daily basis struggle to get by in the current climate. This means that the purpose of the study is to

determine the financial situation of the daily wage workers in Hulfdorf, Colombo-12 during this time. Despite several interviews and in-depth interviews, important information was obtained from 54 regular paid employees. Different descriptive facets of the data collected were discussed. They thus experience severe financial difficulty. Additionally, they don't get enough help, resources, or money during this crisis.

Prof. Rajni Pathak, Prof. Punam Salunkhe “**A research study on Customer expectation and satisfaction level of Urban Clap in beauty services with special reference to Pune.**”,2015[3] This research paper aims to comprehend Pune-based Urban Clap's (in beauty services) level of client satisfaction and client expectations. It reveals how expectations affect service quality in a significant way. Today, it's common knowledge that meeting or exceeding client expectations is a sign of high-quality service. There is a huge demand for online services and delivery services due to the boom in e-commerce and the fast-paced lifestyle. Customers utilise a variety of services, including transportation, food, personal care, and health. Home services will always be required, but in addition to services, customer happiness in this industry is also crucial for companies to thrive.

Pranjal Srivastav, Himanshu gupta “**Roles and Application of digital marketing in digital era**”,2021[4] This essay emphasises the function and use of digital marketing to show how timely it is today. It starts with an overview of digital marketing, its benefits, and the procedures involved. After that, it calculates the procedures' steps before calculating the security risks associated with them. The task has become simpler in the digital age for all industries, including retail. The means of marketing enterprises and selling items have fundamentally altered since the advent of digital marketing in the 1990s, and they have experienced rapid expansion in recent years. Digital marketing offers a glimmer of hope that businesses may prosper in the current environment of the coronavirus outbreak, when physical contact is risky and individuals are more active online on numerous social media platforms.

V. EXISTING APPLICATIONS

Customers can book home services and at-home beauty services through **Urban Company**, an Indian marketplace. By making significant investments in gaining customers' trust, the organisation set itself apart. The company invested in educating and assisting the service providers, becoming actively involved in the process of service delivery, as opposed to simply marketing itself as a platform for lead generation, like many other marketplace platforms like Uber, Airbnb, and Trip Advisor have done. The company's founders believed that this strategy would ultimately result in a more sustainable business model, despite the fact that it increased costs and hindered the company's growth. The business strategy of The Urban Company is uncomplicated and clear-cut. This will link users to the services they need at home. The business assists you in hiring beauticians, personal trainers for exercise, teachers, electricians, plumbers, photographers, and many other professionals. It is a full-stack startup that does automated matchmaking using

algorithms. The company ensures public safety to increase the platform's credibility. The business conducts background investigations and police verification on each and every service provider. With its dual business strategy, The Urban Company is expanding and winning over clients' trust.

VI. METHODOLOGY

A. Working

The users of this app are customer (request for service) and the service providers (provides service). The customer and service provider have to register themselves on the app. If already they have an account then they can log in. The admin will manage bookings, transactions and verify the profiles. The customers will browse services and select desired services as per that admin will assign them the available service providers. If the service providers accept the request then App will notify the customer. After that admin will send payment request to the customer. Customer pays to the admin and his/her booking will be confirmed. After completion of the work, customers can give feedback and ratings, Workers can edit their profile which will include skills work timings and price as per work

B. Design

A horizontal ellipse known as a use case diagram represents a series of actions that give an actor something of quantifiable value. An actor is a person or external system that takes part in one or more interactions with the system. Actors are represented by stick figures. Use case diagrams show relationships between actors and use cases using solid lines. There is a connection when an actor takes part in a use case-specific interaction. The arrowhead is frequently used to symbolise the start of a connection or a significant individual in a use case.

Fig. 1: Use-case diagram of admin

Fig. 2: Use-case diagram of customer

Fig. 3: Use-case diagram of Service provider

A sequence diagram is a diagram created using the Unified Modeling Language (UML) that shows the flow of messages sent and received by objects during an interaction. The order in which messages are transferred between objects is depicted in a sequence diagram. Sequence Diagrams are time-focused, and they graphically depict the interaction's order by using the vertical axis to illustrate the timing of when messages are transmitted. The components of the interaction are displayed on the horizontal axis. According to their participation in the message sequence, the objects participating in the operation are enumerated from left to right. The components on the horizontal axis, however, can appear in any sequence.

Fig. 4: Sequence diagram for booking services

Similar to a flowchart or data flow diagram, an activity diagram graphically depicts the sequence of events or control flow in a system. In business process modelling, activity diagrams are frequently employed. Additionally, they can outline the procedures in a use case diagram. Both sequential and concurrent activities can be described. An activity diagram will always have a start (an initial state) and an end (a final state). Activity diagrams show how multiple levels of abstraction of activities are coordinated to produce a service. Typically, several activities are required to accomplish an event, especially when those operations are intended to accomplish a number of distinct tasks that call for coordination or when there is a relationship between the events in a single use case.

Fig. 5: Activity diagram for Login

VII. CONCLUSION

The suggested system offers a multitude of services by delivering one-click service professionals to your door, which lessens the stress of finding in-house solutions for services. System clients have simple access to our services in a more pleasant manner thanks to a well-organized mobile space. We handle all of your home's cleaning, plumbing, furniture upkeep, electrical work, electrical repairs, house painting, car service, and many more tasks that must be completed as quickly and easily as possible by clicking from anywhere at any time. By incorporating resources like cell phone and computer repair, laundry facilities, food utilities, and much more, the system might last for a very long period in the future.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Shahrzad Shahriari, Mohammadreza Shahriari, Saeidgheiji. " E Commerce And It Impacts on Global Trend And Market". International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah. Vol.3 (Iss.4): April, 2015.
- [2.] L. Richard Ye, Yue Jeff Zhang, Dat-Dao Nguyen, James Chiu, "Fee-based online services: Exploring consumers' willingness to pay". Journal of International Technology and Information Management.
- [3.] Bo Zhang, Ruihan Yong, Meizi Li, Jianguo Pan, JifengHuanglaa, "A Hybrid Trust Evaluation Framework for E-commerce in Online Social Network: ". 2169-3536 (c) 2016 IEEE. Translations and content mining are permitted for academic research
- [4.] Chenggang Zhen,Peng Cheng. "Construction of campus trading platform based on third-party online payment " 2nd International Conference on Industrial and Information Systems,IEEE,2010
- [5.] Sujit Kumar Basak, Irene Govender."Examining the Impact of Privacy, Security, and Trust on the TAM and TTF Models for Ecommerce Consumers: A Pilot Study",IEEE, 2009
- [6.] CAIYrnn-ping, WANG Yuying, "Simple Said about Online Payment Risks and Preventive Measure ", China located International Conference on Infonation Systems for Crisis Response and Management,IEEE,2010
- [7.] DejanKovachev and Ralf Klammadriano, " Beyond the Client Server Architectures: A Survey of Mobile Cloud Techniques ",workshop on mobile computing in 2011.

Fig. 6: Activity diagram of Accept/Cancel service request

C. E-R Diagram

The relationship between individuals, things, locations, concepts, or events inside an information system is depicted graphically in an entity-relationship diagram (ERD). A relation database can be built on top of an ERD, a data modelling technique that can be used to describe business processes.

Fig. 7: E-R Diagram